

CROATIAN DIASPORA IN CANADA: STUDENTS' ATTITUDES TOWARD STUDYING IN CROATIA

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Abstract:

This paper establishes a theoretical framework for transnational educational mobility of Croatian descendants in Canada. This study is analyzing pull factors and motivation for studying in Croatia for a second and third generation descendants of Croatian immigrants - high school students from Mississauga, Ontario. The survey questions, thus, have targeted opinions of young diaspora students in regards to their intent to study in Croatia. This study also inquired about written and spoken knowledge of the Croatian language among the study's participants. Language is presented as an integrative factor for Croatian diaspora members as it connects them with their culture and national identity. The goal of this research study was to examine and analyse the role of the diaspora in the process of internationalisation of the University of Zagreb. Furthermore, the study investigated the potential of transnational social fields within Croatian diaspora in Canada. Cultural value in the research is identified as an influential factor on brand image in the high education.

Keywords: Croatia, diaspora, Canada, students, university, education, transnational

1. Introduction

The literature on transnational social space and transnational field (Kuti, Božić, 2016; Božić, 2001) identifies education as one of the markers of the cultural sphere of

transnational activities (Al-Ali and others 2001). As such, education represents an integral connection between members of the Croatian diaspora in Canada and their country of origin.

This paper establishes a theoretical framework for transnational educational mobility of Croatian descendants in Canada. This type of mobility is framed by formalized activities –such as the potential for high school students from the Dufferin-Peel International Languages Credit Course to study at the University of Zagreb in Croatia. Here, the transnational community is characterized by close symbolic connections which are based in language as well as the national identity of the country of their heritage—thus knowledge of the language is crucial.

Language is always a matter of symbols that, in turn, are connected to meaning. In this paper, the language used, could, therefore, be viewed both as inclusive and exclusive, depending on the point of view (Ryan, 1979:147). The language could be perceived as inclusive when it is regarded as a sum of symbols which are placed within the other language (dominant). On the other hand, when the language is perceived as the one which disables direct communication with the other languages groups in the same territory, it is considered exclusive. Based on sociolinguistic premises, the Croatian language and language fluency among Croatian diaspora in Canadian society should be viewed as the basis for seeking answers of why people of Croatian descent show interest to study in Croatia, and how and why they maintained so many heritage languages schools and organizations in Canada. Within the context of migration, language and culture intersect, particularly in the light of our research which has indicated a desire in second and third generation diaspora students to continue their education at the University of Zagreb.

Research concerning ethnolinguistic vitality allows us to assess the stability of both minority groups and minority language, where the marker of ethnolinguistic vitality is the capacity of one ethnic group to survive as a single identity amongst other language identities. (Giles, Bourhis and Taylor, 1977: 308). It is measured through three structural variables – demographic, status and variable of institutional support. Throughout our research, we focused on institutional support provided by the country of origin for Croatian descendants in Canada, through special allocations for diaspora students for the academic year 2018/2019 at the University of Zagreb.

Fishman's observation (Fishman, 1972, 1991) about the crucial role of the family and home domain in the transmission and preservation of minority language informed many of our questions regarding the preservation of language fluency of Croatian language speakers. According to this study, the separation from home has been determined as a main obstacle to leaving the family home in order to continue studies in Croatia. In this way, the preservation of minority language is not possible without intragenerational transmission just as Fishman (1991: 113) asserts. Clyne (2003: 22), meanwhile, stresses the necessity of communicating in the Croatian language within the family homes of diaspora students in Canada. Hence, it is necessary to understand the process of the preservation of the Croatian language among second and third generation of Croatian immigrants through the intragenerational and intergenerational

methods. A historical overview of Croatian heritage language schools has been supplied, alongside their positioning within the mainstream education system. While conducting this overview, it was observed that a new form of cosmopolitanism, emerging in the theories of supranational forms of existence, has materialized. Some authors call this trend "*global citizenship*" (Linklater, 1998; Carter, 2001), which includes the diaspora. A general intersection of postmodern social theory is the hypothesis of cultural diversity of modern societies, which serves as a base for understanding multiculturalism (comp. Kymlicka, 2003).

Although this type of diaspora partially implicates the transformation of nation-states and the deviation from national monopolies regarding their belonging to the land of origin, our purposes allow us to use the studies of transnationalism which are not directly related to ideological or legal transcending of nation-state (Linklater, 1998; Carter, 2001). In this context, we can observe a new type of diaspora – transnational diaspora. This type of diaspora relates to diaspora's social morphology in transnational public field of mobility of post-secondary education. Of course, transnationalism in this context could also be conditionally viewed as a new form of cosmopolitanism. There are a few reasons for this line of inquiry. Transnationalism still lacks a clear theoretical framework (Portes, Guarnizo i Landolt, 1999), and has been a fragmented area of study even up until the end of the late 19th century. Steven Vertovec (1999: 449–456) has attempted to find new methods of research applying to the whole field of transnationalism, such as new forms of awareness, which relate to the construction of new identities, as well as the possibility of political involvement through transnational social movements (Božić, 2004; Vertovec, 2003). In order for a community to gain a high level of social cohesion and a common repertoire of symbolic and collective representations, Faist sets aside collective representations, or "*common ideas, beliefs, judgements and symbols... which can be represented in a some sort of collective identity*" (Faist, 2000: 109).

Thus, it is important to establish a distinct difference between solidarity directed to creating real social ties and diffusive solidarity, which is related to "*larger groups such as territorial and symbolic communities.... in which members and participants mostly don't have immediate contact*" (Faist, 2000: 109). Therefore, a cultural pluralism hypothesis for modern society, which is the starting point in the understanding of both multiculturalism and transnational diaspora, becomes one of the common grounds of (post)modern social theory (usp. Kymlicka, 2003). It is thus important to stress how the position of minority identities has been established, especially when public discussion was conducted as early as in the 1980s and 1990s. Even today, the EU has been facing a crisis caused by polarization of two views – the strengthening of national cultural identities and multiculturalism (Sršen, 2013).

Most definitions of multiculturalism have one thing in common: a statement or a premise that culture is a certainty of life and that multiculturalism strives to protect cultural differences (Sršen, 2014: 106). Cultural differences are social phenomena, despite their multilayered nature, and are also an object of theorizing, empirical

research and political decision (Kivisto, 2002). The line of inquiry in this paper employs modes of existence in some transnational social fields with the land of origin.

2. History of the Croatian International Credit Course (CICC) in Ontario

The Croatian International Credit Course (CICC) was offered for the first time during the 1988-1989 academic year, upon the approval of the Ontario Ministry of Education and that of the Continuing Education Department of DPCDSB. In 1989-1990, *Hrvatski II* (Croatian Two) was introduced and taught at the same locations, and at the beginning of the following year the Ontario Academic Credit Course (OAC) program began. All three programs have been approved and accepted by the Ontario Ministry of Education as elective high school credit courses, which meant that students could take courses during their high school years and count them towards the total of thirty courses needed to graduate. In those early years, an average of 150 students completed the program each year. This program grew out of the first International Language program, which was introduced into the Toronto Catholic District School Board in 1976. This contribution to Multicultural policy was historic, and is intended for funding heritage language instruction for schools of various ethnic groups. Since its inception, the credit program in the Toronto Catholic Board was led by Vinko Grubišić. He acknowledged the lobbying efforts of a number of Croatians who had previously reached out to then Minister of Education Betty Stevenson, and was able to call the course by its Croatian name, although Croatia was at the time a republic within the Yugoslav federation.

The beginning of 1977-1978 school year in Toronto was also marked by the publication of the textbook *Učimo hrvatski izvan Hrvatske* (Learning Croatian outside Croatia), and it was the result of a sustained effort to create a curriculum specifically designed to suit the needs of students whose first language may no longer be Croatian. With the creation of the Chair of Croatian Studies at the University of Waterloo in 1988, students gained an opportunity to study Croatian at all three levels of the educational system. The program offered three levels of study (beginner, intermediate, and advanced), as well as a correspondence option to Croatians living outside of Canada. The program's first chair was Professor Vinko Grubišićⁱ, who completed two textbooks *Elementary Croatian 1* (1999) and *Elementary Croatian 2* (1999). In 1997, Grubišić also published *Croatian Reader* along with Anita Mikulić-Kovačević. As the number of students in the program is dwindling, the program's need and urgency to adjust to the changing dynamics of the Croatian-Canadian diaspora in Ontario schools is apparent.

3. Methodology

The goal of this study was to analyse the role of diaspora in the process of internationalisation of the University of Zagreb through the factor of return migration.

ⁱ Vinko Grubišić, professor emeritus, University of Waterloo, poet, playwright, essayist, translator. He has authored many textbooks and readers for Croatian language teaching over the last forty years of his teaching Croatian language at high school and university level.

The case study was conducted through quantitative researchⁱⁱ with the aim to achieve the aforementioned research objective. An exploratory case study elaborates and tests theoretical concepts of transnationalism and multiculturalism and its ties to the concept of diaspora mobility as an alternative model of social integration. Through an analysis of identity elements within the theory, the new ideal-typical model of diaspora emerges, based on the specific relationship towards identity. It is important to stress that each construction of identity, including the Croatian identity, always contains dihotomies: inside/, outside, individual / group, individual / social, / other (Sršen, Piskač, 2012: 6). The study conducted for this type of diaspora looked into the University of Zagreb's potential for internationalisation. The focus group was second and third generation Croatian-Canadian high school students in Mississauga, ON, Canada. The relevance of this case study is in accordance with the population or sample of the researched group. Namely, second and third generation Croatian Canadians in Mississauga were represented as the case (example, item), and precisely explain the theoretical concept and additional updates used in testing in this case study.

3.1 Applied Research Methods

Research of Croatian diaspora involves some difficulties, namely because geographical distances, which limits an expanse of the research topic. Given that this case study research was conducted by three authors, only one was physically present for the field research. In depth, qualitative research would require more substantial sources in regards to the research conducted. The authors have been successful in interpreting their research goals based on the value of the data gathered through quantitative case study method. In this study, data was gathered through the use of a survey. While case studies that are based on quantitative approaches are generally used less frequently than qualitative approaches (Yin, 2012) for researching immigration and diaspora issues, this approach optimizes methodological requirements, as well as efficiency in processing of available data. As mentioned earlier, we used a survey technique, which consisted of two areas of measure. The first area of measure was the students' familiarity with everyday life in Croatia, such as politics, social relations, and the economy. In addition, it contained questions relating to national / ethnic identifiers of the examinee as a member of the diaspora. All questions in this instrument were measured on a scale of 1 to 5, and based on the principle of so called Likert scale (strongly agree, agree, neither agree nor disagree, disagree, strongly disagree). The second area of measure in this study is focused on students' attitudes about studying at University of Zagreb, as well as possible obstacles to their attendance (studying, participation) at the University of Zagreb. The survey contained 16 questions and 37 variables, which will be analyzed based on descriptive statistics and correlative relations between questions of the two areas of measure.

ⁱⁱ Explorative case study implies a link with a case of the research which tested a theoretical concept and placed this case in the wider interactive social landscape. In other words, it examines a model of functioning of the specific case through the appropriate context (Tellis, 1997).

Figure 1: Graphic Organizer

3.2 Research Sample

The research sample was chosen deliberately, based on the main premises surrounding the student population which participated in this research – high school students at *Father Michael Goetz CSS, Dufferin-Peel Catholic Distric School Board*. The survey included all students in the program who are of second and third generation Croatian descent. Altogether, 44 questionnaires were collected. Moreover, the survey was conducted following the principles of ethical social research. A field study was carried out within a month-long time frame. Further, the socio-demographical aspect of the study encompassed an approximately equal number of male and female examinees, consisting of 23 female participants and 21 male participants. Also, the study intended to survey students who wish to pursue postsecondary education after high school, which was indicated by 35 participants, alongside three who did not intend to pursue post-secondary education and six who were uncertain. In order to test and supplement our presupposed theory and to successfully fulfill all our research targets, we set out the following hypothesis:

- 1) Survey participants are not familiar with current events in Croatia.
- 2) Survey participants wish (desire) to attend University of Zagreb.
- 3) Survey participants are familiar with spoken and written Croatian language.
- 4) The main obstacle to attending University of Zagreb is a financial one.
- 5) There exists a statistically significant correlation between the age of students and desire to attend University of Zagreb.

3.3 Familiarity with Current Events in Croatia

Throughout this study, it was crucial to examine the main aspects of each participant's national identity. The main components of Croatian diaspora identities were primarily tested through inquiry into elements of collective identity.

In the set of questions designed to test the participants' knowledge of Croatian culture, as it is shown in Chart 1.1, participants deemed their knowledge of culture (86,4) as good, or very good. It is important to stress that affiliation and familiarity with Croatian

culture could be perceived as relative in the context of this study. Moreover, this research study stresses importance of participants' self-assessment in terms of what they consider Croatian culture.

Chart 1.1: Familiarity with Croatian Culture

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Disagree	2	4,5	4,5	4,5
	Neither agree, or disagree	4	9,1	9,1	13,6
	Agree	12	27,3	27,3	40,9
	Strongly agree	26	59,1	59,1	100,0
	Total	44	100,0	100,0	

The survey participants were also confident of their knowledge of Croatian history, based on their self-assessment (see Chart 1.2). However, it is important to note that they were more familiar with Croatian culture than with Croatian history. Therefore, this is an indication of a connection between culture and history as defining factors of the diaspora identity.

Traditional principles of a certain culture were determined in historical continuity (Grbić, 1994). As a remark, in both charts (1.1 and 1.2) none of the participants indicated that they are "not at all familiar" in this category.

Chart 1.2: Familiarity with Croatian History

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Not Familiar	4	9,1	9,1	9,1
	Neither familiar, or Not familiar	12	27,3	27,3	36,4
	Moderately familiar	18	40,9	40,9	77,3
	Extremely familiar	10	22,7	22,7	100,0
	Total	44	100,0	100,0	

On the other hand, when asked about their familiarity with both the political and economic situation in Croatia, participants were less informed about current events. For example, 40.9 percent (Chart 1.3) of surveyed participants knew about the political situation in Croatia, while only 31,9 percent (Chart 1.4) of participants were familiar with economic trends in Croatia.

In addition, there is a statistically important correlation between the familiarity with Croatian culture and history (0,554) and between the familiarity with political and economic situation in Croatia (0,733). In addition, the unfamiliarity with both the political and economic situation holds great importance for this study (29,5% of participants for political situation and 34,1% for economic trends).

Chart 1.3: Familiarity with Political Situation in the Republic of Croatia

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Not at all familiar	3	6,8	6,8	6,8
	Not familiar	10	22,7	22,7	29,5
	Neither familiar, or not familiar	13	29,5	29,5	59,1
	Moderately familiar	12	27,3	27,3	86,4
	Extremely familiar	6	13,6	13,6	100,0
	Total	44	100,0	100,0	

Chart 1.4: Familiarity with Economic Situation in the Republic of Croatia

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Not at all familiar	4	9,1	9,1	9,1
	Not familiar	11	25,0	25,0	34,1
	Neither familiar, or not familiar	15	34,1	34,1	68,2
	Somewhat familiar	9	20,5	20,5	88,6
	Extremely familiar	5	11,4	11,4	100,0
	Total	44	100,0	100,0	

3.4 Knowledge and Use of Croatian Language

When defining the Croatian identity, language is of great importance. In order to define the language component of identity of second and third generation Croatian diaspora, the question of familiarity and use of Croatian language was asked (see Charts 2.1 and 2.2). Survey results demonstrated that 77,2 percent of participants hold their knowledge of Croatian language adequate, which contributes to strengthening of language as a component in relation to Croatian national identity. In contrast, when asked about the use of Croatian language, only 11,4% of surveyed participants use language on a weekly basis, and 20,5 per cent on a monthly basis. Most of the participants speak Croatian a few times per year (Chart 2.2).

Chart 2.1: Knowledge of the Spoken Language

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Not familiar	1	2,3	2,3	2,3
	Neither familiar, or not familiar	9	20,5	20,5	22,7
	Somewhat familiar	21	47,7	47,7	70,5
	Extremely familiar	13	29,5	29,5	100,0
	Total	44	100,0	100,0	

Chart 2.2: Frequency of Use of Croatian language

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	A few times per year	5	11,4	11,4	11,4
	A few times per month	9	20,5	20,5	31,8
	A few times per week	23	52,3	52,3	84,1
	Once a year	7	15,9	15,9	100,0
	Total	44	100,0	100,0	

3.5 Studying at University of Zagreb

The second element of this study is the option of attending the University of Zagreb. As such, questions regarding this element examined the possibilities, desires and obstacles for studying at the University of Zagreb. University of Zagreb's appeal, as well as the possibility of joining this University was pertinent to the case study. Overall, out of 44 participants of second and third generation diaspora students, 31.8 percent confirmed that they consider attending the University of Zagreb. Moreover, 20,5 percent of students stated that their attendance at the University of Zagreb is extremely likely.

When we take a closer look at the frequencies, out of 44 participants of second and third generation diaspora students, 14 of them maintain that this is extremely likely. Given the population of Croatian diaspora in Canada, and the contextualism of it, this number illustrates the main potential in attracting members of the Croatian diaspora to their homeland for education.

Chart 3.1: A Possibility of Attending University of Zagreb

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Extremely likely	9	20,5	20,5	20,5
	Likely	5	11,4	11,4	31,8
	Neutral	17	38,6	38,6	70,5
	Unlikely	11	25,0	25,0	95,5
	Extremely unlikely	2	4,5	4,5	100,0
	Total	44	100,0	100,0	

Those who responded that they would not likely attend the University of Zagreb were either undecided or indicated significant obstacles to their attendance at Uof Z. In Chart 3.2, 23,8% of participants indicated financial issues as the main reason for not attending the University of Zagreb, while separation from family was the main reason for 28,6% of participants. Out of all other responses, these two reasons were most common.

Chart 3.2: The Main Obstacles to Attending University of Zagreb

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Financial issues	5	11,4	23,8	23,8
	Separation from the family	6	13,6	28,6	52,4
	Lack of interest	2	4,5	9,5	61,9
	Fear of unknown	1	2,3	4,8	66,7
	Lack of information about the possibilities of studying at University of Zagreb	3	6,8	14,3	81,0
	Insufficient language fluency	3	6,8	14,3	95,2
	Other	1	2,3	4,8	100,0
	Total	21	47,7	100,0	
Missing	999	23	52,3		
Total		44	100,0		

The quota information for 54,8 % of participants is extremely important, and has proportionally increased with the likelihood of attending University of Zagreb. However, the correlation between interest to attend the University of Zagreb and the importance of information about quotas is statistically important (606). The significant frequency of the participants in terms of quotas for diaspora students were undecided - 31,5% of participants was neutral on this question.

Chart 3.3: How Important Is the Information about Quotas for Diaspora Students

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Very important	3	6,8	7,1	7,1
	Important	20	45,5	47,6	54,8
	Neutral	13	29,5	31,0	85,7
	Not at all important	6	13,6	14,3	100,0
	Total	42	95,5	100,0	
Missing	999	2	4,5		
Total		44	100,0		

3.6 Correlational Linking in Case Study Research

This study has demonstrated correlations of the two areas of interest. First and foremost, it displayed statistically significant correlations in connection with main hypothesis of the research study. Chart 4.1 shows a statistically significant moderate negative correlation between the age of participants and importance of information about quotas for diaspora students. With older students, it was less important to gain information about quotas. Thus, we rejected the key research hypothesis which was founded on proportionality, e.g. positive correlation between age and importance of receiving information about quotas for diaspora students at University of Zagreb.

Chart 4.1: Correlations

			Age	How important is information about quotas
Spearman's rho	Age	Correlation Coefficient	1,000	-,305*
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	,050
		N	44	42
	How important is information about quotas	Correlation Coefficient	-,305*	1,000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	,050	.
		N	42	42

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

This research showed a mild negative correlation between one's knowledge of Croatian history and culture in relation to aspiration and possibility to study at University of Zagreb (-0,312 culture and -0,444, see Chart 4.2). It was observed that, based on a significance of 0,05, the participants who were more familiar with Croatian history and culture would find it more difficult to choose to study at the University of Zagreb. With that said, we have dismissed our second hypothesis of this study, which presumed that

familiarity with history and culture is the main factor in defining a desire to study in Republic of Croatia. Thus, we confirmed our hypothesis that there is a desire to embrace the identity.

Chart 4.2: Correlations

		Age	How important is information about quotas	
Spearman's rho	Age	Correlation Coefficient	1,000	
		Sig. (2-tailed)	,305*	
		N	44	
	How important is information about quotas	Correlation Coefficient	-,305*	1,000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	,050	.
		N	42	42

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

4. Discussion

Through an elaborate research analysis, we tested the connections towards the presumed case study's hypothesis. The first hypothesis in this study, for instance, reputed that participants were not familiar with current events in the Republic of Croatia, which was to some extent confirmed. Difference in familiarity with current events was obvious in the dimensions of social reality: participants were better informed about the country's political situation (40,9%) than with its economic situation (31,9%). On the other hand, the high rate of familiarity was measured among study participants in relation to their familiarity with Croatian history (63,6%). Knowledge of Croatian history also shows a moderately negative statistically important correlation with the possibility of studying in Croatia. This fact could be theoretically tested with additional integration elements, such as multiculturalism in Canadian society. Likewise, the integration link for Croatian diaspora members in Canada with Croatian identity (which manifests symbolically through learning about Croatian tradition and history) has been sufficient for preservation of integration mechanisms. This theoretical framework can partially explain a negative correlation of these two variables. Furthermore, a relatively close negative correlation could be found in relation to age and desire to pursue studies in Croatia. A successful integration in Canadian society through certain time spans creates a cohesive educational environment that most participants are unwilling to change. Attending the University of Zagreb, as a second hypothesis of this case study, has been partially attested. A probability of studying in Croatia for the researched group of participants was 31.0%. A high rate of probability epitomises ties with both Croatian identity, and cultural and traditional values.

Moreover, the survey participants who consider their attendance at the University of Zagreb less likely have stressed that they would not go because of separation from the family (28,6%). The financial situation is the second most important factor (23,8%) among obstacles to attending the University of Zagreb. Based on these

findings, the last hypothesis about reasons for not attending the University of Zagreb was rejected. The importance of family life was substantiated in Fishersman's observation about the key role of the family in preserving of some of national identifying factors (1972, 1991)

This study also inquired about written and spoken knowledge of the Croatian language among the study's participants. As such, language is perceived as an inclusive but also an exclusive symbol. On one hand, the exclusive dimension has been presented in frequency of the second language use: 52,3% of participants use Croatian language only a few times per year, which seems consistent with family gatherings and celebrations around major holidays. Only 11,4 % of participants use the Croatian language a few times per week, while none stated that they use the language daily. Overall, spoken language fluency demonstrates a successful integration trend of members of the Croatian diaspora in a multicultural environment.

5. Conclusion

The goal of this research study was to examine and analyse the role of the diaspora in the process of internationalisation of the University of Zagreb. Furthermore, the study investigated the potential of transnational social fields within Croatian diaspora in Canada. The research showed that there are a significant number of study participants who were willing to attend University of Zagreb. It is important to stress, however, that the participants were attending high school and most of them already had the intention of pursuing a post-secondary education. Attending the University of Zagreb correlates with certain variables and factors.

First and foremost, it is important to stress the significant level of integration of the Croatian diaspora into mainstream Canadian society. Better integration results in limited possibilities for attending university abroad due to social (family and friendships) relationships in Canada. Separation from one's family emerged as one of the main reasons of not to attend the University of Zagreb, followed by financial issues. Ultimately, language is presented as an integrative factor for Croatian diaspora members as it connects them with their culture and national identity. A high rate of heritage language proficiency among participants indicates opportunities for further development of the transnational field, which enables exceptional educational potential for both Croatian diaspora youth and Croatian Universities.

International exchange and attendance at the University of Zagreb for Croatian diaspora youth is a topic that should be further supported, both through research and projects that aim to strengthen the transnational Croatian identity, which can attain enrichment through participation in Canada's dynamic multicultural society.

In sum, this paper argues that we need to move beyond simple recognition of a symbiotic relationship between nationalism and transnationalism. Cultural value is identified as an influential factor on brand image in the high education. According to this branding of national values in diaspora in the transnational social space is meant to represent the nation's distinct and unique value among diverse international publics,

especially scholars. But there is a distinct lack of understanding of these relationships in a modern diaspora context.

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